

From Public Servants to Co-creators: Design of MINCETUR Lab with the Fab City Full Stack methodology to innovate the tourism sector

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Abstract

MINCETUR Lab is a laboratory created by the Ministry of Foreign Trade and Tourism of Peru (MINCETUR) to promote innovation, creativity, and sustainability in the tourism sector through the use of digital technologies, public innovation, creative economy, and science and technology. The lab aims to foster collaboration among stakeholders in the tourism industry, close digital gaps in the sector, leverage Peru's cultural and creative assets, and promote research, development, and innovation in science and technology fields for the tourism industry. MINCETUR Lab is designed using the Fab City Full Stack methodology learned during the Master in Design for Distributed Innovation (MDDI) from the Institute for Advanced Architecture of Catalonia and the Fab City Foundation, emphasising digital social innovation, as well as collaboration to address global challenges.

The paper shows the application of the methodology for its design and implementation, exploring each of its levels, challenges and strategies during the creation process, affecting the role of public servants as active agents in the generation of innovation proposals through collaborative work with internal and external stakeholders from public, private and educational sectors, as well as citizens and the Fab Lab network.

Keywords

Tourism, creative economy, public innovation, public sector, Full Stack

1 Introduction

The Ministry of Foreign Trade and Tourism of Peru- MINCETUR - defines, directs, executes, coordinates and supervises foreign trade and tourism policies. It is responsible for the promotion of exports and international trade negotiations. In terms of tourism, it promotes, guides and regulates tourism activity and crafts. It is located in Lima, the capital of Peru, with an impact not only in the country but different parts of the world. The ministry operates thanks to 250 public servants distributed in different areas with specific roles who become decision-makers for the design and implementation of new strategies focused on innovation and competitiveness in the tourism and handicraft sector.

MINCETUR, as part of its structure, is divided in different areas: the Vice Ministry of Tourism, the Vice Ministry of Foreign Trade, the General Secretariat, and affiliated entities such as PROMPERU (a public promotion agency), Plan Copesco (infrastructure for accessibility) and CENFOTUR (education). That physical and organisational division and the inexistence of a space to learn and share from different perspectives, methodologies and technologies make that public servants do not communicate and keep their ideas and projects for themselves. This disconnection also affects the cooperation between its public servants and their stakeholders from private, public, and education sectors worldwide. For that reason, the Direction of Innovation of the Tourist Offer from the Vice Ministry of Tourism has designed a laboratory, MINCETUR Lab, applying Fab City's Full Stack methodology and exploring creativity and innovation methodologies based on 4 important axes: digital transformation, public innovation, creative economies and science, technology and technological innovation. Currently, the space is in the process of being formalised through a ministerial resolution and the leading team participating on its creation is made up of a tourism specialist with experience in public management, a specialist in smart tourist destinations and an industrial designer with studies of distributed and experience design.

2 Background

The concept of innovation has evolved during the last decades according to the context and evidence reflected in the economy, therefore, it is not a static concept. There are organisations globally that have dedicated themselves to research and possible definition of the concept and explored the possibilities to include that as part of their functions with the meaning of improving their products and services. In terms of definition of “innovation”, one of the main references is the Oslo Manual, which was created thanks to the collaboration between the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) and the European Statistical Office (Eurostat), recognized for producing data on the European Union and promoting the exchange and agreement between the different countries regarding the use of statistical methods. The Oslo Manual has 4 versions published in the years 1992, 1997, 2005 and 2018, being the result of the participation of international organisations in the OECD Working Party of National Experts on Science and Technology Indicators (NESTI). Innovation can be defined as “...a new or improved product or process (or a combination thereof) that differs significantly from the unit's previous products or processes and that has been made available to potential users (product) or put into use by the unit (process)” (OECD/Eurostat, 2018).

Likewise, the Global Innovation Index (GII) is a document prepared by different international organisations, the main ones being the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO) and the SC Johnson College of Business at Cornell University in the United States. The GII is based on the collection and analysis of information from different entities at a global level, showing the relative position compared to 132 economies through 81 indicators divided into 7 pillars: institutions, human capital and research, infrastructure, market sophistication, sophistication of business, technological knowledge and results, and creative results (WIPO, 2022).

Although Peru is ranked 65th in the ranking (2022), the Global Innovation Index measures a series of aspects thanks to data from public and private organisations globally and the perception of those surveyed, including criteria such as the diffusion of knowledge, creative goods and services, education, research and development, political climate, knowledge absorption, among others.

Specifically in the tourism sector, the Travel and Tourism Competitiveness Index 2021 -TTDI prepared by the World Economic Forum is also considered. According to the dataset, the Peruvian economy is ranked 65 out of 117, with opportunities for improvement such as the quality of urban centers, investment in green energy and infrastructure, or the conservation of species (Uppink, L., & Soshkin, M., 2022).

Regarding public Peruvian entities, the National Council of Science, Technology and Technological Innovation from Peru- CONCYTEC- developed the National Science, Technology and Innovation Policy (CTI) of Peru in 2016, which defined a set of guidelines and strategies to promote the development of science, technology and innovation in the country, its main objectives being the promotion of quality scientific and technological research in the country, the promotion of innovation and entrepreneurship at the national

level, strengthening the scientific and technological capacity of the country's public and private institutions and establishing alliances and collaborations with international institutions and organisations to strengthen CTI in the country.

According to the Regional Competitiveness Index of Peru (ICRP) 2021, a document prepared by CENTRUM PUCP that measures the ability of the 26 regions of Peru to manage all of their resources and skills in order to raise their productivity and increase the well-being of their population, none of the country's regions has a high level of competitiveness. It shows that 5 Peruvian regions are at very low levels and 20 regions at extreme low levels (Marquina, et al., 2021). Although Lima is in first place for its results in skills and competencies, centralism is still shown in its development and in properly implemented public services, meaning a physical, emotional, labour and opportunities disconnection with citizens outside the capital.

Before the COVID-19 pandemic, that is, until 2019, the tourism sector represented 3.9% of the national GDP, generating almost 1.5 million jobs directly and indirectly, being the third foreign exchange generator with a significant contribution to the balance of payments at US \$4,703 million. The pandemic produced a reduction in tourism GDP by almost half, also contracting foreign exchange to US\$1,002 million, -78.7% compared to 2019. In 2020, the arrival of international tourists to Peru fell compared to 2019; additionally, the flow of domestic tourism trips fell 70.4%.

In this context, the OECD published the document "Preparing the Tourism Workforce for the Digital Future" indicating that "employers saw gaps mainly in softer skills, such as language, interpersonal skills and basic information and communication technology skills, all not necessarily specific to tourism" (OECD, 2021). Challenges are also mentioned such as "the effects of automation on employment, the need to retrain the workforce for the digital economy and create a safety net for workers in precarious working conditions (such as platform workers or temporary jobs). It is stated that in view of the emergence of technologies it is important to strengthen skills such as:

- Analytical thinking and innovation.
- Active learning and learning strategies.
- Creativity, originality and initiative.
- Technology design and programming
- Creative thinking and analysis.
- Resolution of complex problems.
- Leadership and social influence
- emotional intelligence

In this sense, tourist activity has become one of the most affected sectors of the national economy. Given the urgent need for intervention by the Peruvian State, Law No. 31103 was promulgated, "Law that declares the reactivation of the tourism sector of national interest and establishes measures for its sustainable development." Within this regulatory framework, the "National Strategy for the Reactivation of the Tourism Sector 2021 - 2023" was approved; however, due to the extension of the State of National Emergency and the projections of recovery of international and national tourism, the strategy was reconsidered and its horizon extended to the year 2025, which gave rise to the "National Strategy for the Reactivation of the Tourism Sector 2022 - 2025". In order to develop a territorial approach in the strategy, the new market trends were made visible, as well as the priority and recurring needs presented by the public and private sectors. As part of the National Strategy, the line of action 3.1 is set to promote technology transfer in the tourism value chain with the strategic actions.

3 MINCETUR Lab

From the Direction of Innovation of the Tourist Offer of the Vice Ministry of Tourism of MINCETUR in Peru, applying the Fab City Full Stack and with the participation of MINCETUR public servants, it was identified the need to design spaces and physical and digital moments that allow not only the exploration of the main challenges of the tourism and craft sector, but also the co-creation and approach of new or better

proposals for solutions to different problems, needs and pains, using collaborative and multidisciplinary work among all the identified stakeholders from the public, private, academic sectors, with an important intervention of the civil society.

Based on that, there was an exploration of solutions and concepts coming to the word "laboratory" which is as a space in which (i) key problems, priorities and tasks are sought and identified, (ii) ideas that have an impact on these areas are developed, (iii) tests and prototypes of solutions are carried out, and (iv) new entry points or routes are created to drive changes in the systems or have a greater impact (Murray, R. et al, 2010).

Creativity, communication, collaboration, critical thinking, perseverance, digital skills, and social and cultural concern become the main skills strengthened in these new spaces, through the application of new design methodologies and experimentation with information and communication technologies, which would allow the development of new tourist products and experiences, as well as the reduction of digital gaps in MINCETUR users and those actors directly or indirectly linked to the tourism and craft sector.

The Open Knowledge blog of the Inter-American Development Bank- IDB affirms that innovation laboratories are "spaces to experiment with new ways of generating public value, modernising the relationship with citizens, providing new channels of participation and collaboration" (Paonessa, L., 2017). In addition, according to the publication "Innovating for better management: The contribution of public innovation laboratories" of the IDB, some common characteristics of the laboratories are that their human teams are not afraid of failure, the members work with the user's perspective, multidisciplinary teams are formed and they open spaces for collaboration and co-creation.

In this way and with the participation and feedback from MINCETUR public servants, MINCETUR Lab emerges, a laboratory-space with new ways of generating public value from the Direction of Innovation of the Tourist Offer, where collaborative methodologies (co-creation and distributed design) are used, promoting the development and implementation of solutions to improve services linked to the sector and the adoption of innovative practices with a multidisciplinary approach focused on people and the planet.

Through methodologies such as design thinking and double diamond, information and communication technologies and Fab Lab's applications and implications related to 3D printing, CNC milling, electronics production and biomaterials, with a series of software and hardware, applied by MINCETUR Lab, needs are identified and facilitation is provided during the innovation process in products, services and experiences. The results of the experiences can be prototyped or taken to a pilot scale and evaluated in such a way that the use of existing administrative data and contact networks is maximised.

The MINCETUR Lab provides support during the creative process starting with the identification of the need. The initiative makes it possible to discover and understand the needs of the tourism and craft sector through the design, implementation and impact evaluation of improvements. The needs assessment is carried out based on experimental methods, in order to know the user and the market. The methodology makes it possible to more successfully determine the effectiveness of an innovation before deciding to scale it up.

For this, it has also been planned that the laboratory includes the participation of stakeholders coming from the academy (universities and institutes), the public sector and the private sector, national and international researchers, creators and innovators, who will contribute to the design, development, evaluation of processes and results, in addition to a multidisciplinary and intercultural perspective.

4 The 4 axes of MINCETUR Lab

The general objective of MINCETUR Lab is to promote the development of innovative solutions through collaborative and multidisciplinary work to improve the competitiveness of the tourism sector. Additionally, its specific objectives are:

1. Generate spaces and moments for collaboration between different strategic actors in the tourism sector,

2. Identify challenges and opportunities in the tourism sector through the collection and analysis of information, and
3. Contribute to the strengthening of knowledge management focused on the tourism and craft sector.

Faced with the identified needs and opportunities, the MINCETUR Lab initiative arises, with a focus on 4 axes: digital transformation, public innovation, creative economy and science, technology and technological innovation (CTI).

- Digital transformation: It is the continuous, disruptive, strategic and cultural change process that is based on the intensive use of digital technologies, systematisation and analysis of data to generate economic, social and value effects for people.
- Creative economy: It includes economic activities based on knowledge and the interaction between human creativity and ideas, knowledge and technology, as well as cultural values or artistic and cultural heritage and other individual or collective creative expressions.
- Public innovation: It is the inclusive and iterative process to define public problems, co-create, prototype and implement viable solutions that modernise the State and add value to and with people, learning from their feedback, knowledge and support.
- Science, technology and technological innovation: It focuses on the development of technological innovation projects, the use of information systems, the creation of spaces dedicated to technological innovation, the design of products and services linked to technological innovation, and the promotion of the development and publication of scientific articles in indexed journals.

5 Methodology

The design of the project started with the reflection and analysis of the Fab City Full Stack focused on MINCETUR in order to identify the systems, resources and stakeholders connected to the ministry. There was also a development of collaborative work sessions with public servants from the tourism sector of MINCETUR, applying tools such as Mentimeter, Kahoot and Google Form at the end with closed questions to measure the perception of innovation in tourism and to discover their interests, goals, needs, complaints and ideas anonymously. Interviews were conducted with citizens during the protests in Lima due to political conflicts, generating 3 recorded videos on Tiktok entitled: "Do you want to improve the country? Start by accepting that there are problems", "Response from a man from Juliaca during the march. Topic: Education" and "A burnt down Juliaca police station", with a number of 23.9k, 137k and 102.4k views respectively, and 81, 420 and 856 comments each, which confirmed the main problem linked to lack of communication and sense of sharing between public servants and their human & non-human stakeholders.

As part of the exploration carried out through observation and 11 face-to-face and remote interventions with actors from the public, private and academic sectors, different needs and ideas were identified from the perspective of the public servants and stakeholders through the development of dynamics and the collection of information (Table 1).

Table 1: List of interventions, participants and findings

# of intervention in chronological order	Participants (type of intervention)	Findings
1	18 public servants from the Information Technology Office from MINCETUR (in person and remote) (Figure 1)	Superpowers*: creativity, detail, to help, software development, patience, perseverance, share knowledge, to smile, to experiment, to read Needs: -3D design workshop

# of intervention in chronological order	Participants (type of intervention)	Findings
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Arduino -New courses related to their careers/skills -Workshops based on citizens needs -Be part of an innovation network -New methodologies to identify gaps <p>*Despite being an interesting exercise, it was not repeated during the next interventions because of lack of time of participants.</p>
2	18 public servants from Direction of Innovation of the Tourist Offer + Direction of Technological Innovation Centers for Crafts and Tourism + General Direction of Crafts (in person)	<p>Needs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Co-creation workshops -Soft skills workshops -How to get citizens feedback -Innovation labs tour -Innovation workshops based on normativity of law -Agility of process
3	7 citizens (remote by Tiktok)	<p>Ideas:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Critical thinking centred on traditional tourism -Connection of stakeholders with financial resources -Workshops about technologies and applications -Welcome to failure and iterations
4	7 public servants from CONCYTEC and 1 from Presidencia del Consejo de Ministros - PCM (remote)	<p>Ideas*:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Include research and development in the project -Include digital transformation <p>*This intervention had an impact on the project, generating an iteration on the project and including digital transformation and science, technology and technological innovation as axes.</p>
5	12 artisans from Puno (remote)	<p>Needs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Learn digital fabrication based on textiles (alpaca) -Create new products based on their local culture -Connect with the world -Explore new shapes of handicrafts -Experiment with new (bio)materials
6	4 public servants from CONCYTEC (remote)	<p>Results:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Feedback about the alignments of the proposal MINCETUR Lab -Connection of the project with CONCYTEC in terms of research, science, technology, technologic innovation -Idea of creating open calls/challenges for local makers and entrepreneurs (open innovation) -Idea of development of pilots with CONCYTEC users

# of intervention in chronological order	Participants (type of intervention)	Findings
7	MINCETUR in 3D Fashion event (FabLat)	Results: -Connection of MINCETUR public servants with FabLabs and makers -MINCETUR understanding of STEAM definition -Involvement of MINCETUR with a community of creators -Meeting fashion designers and people with disabilities that can be part of MINCETUR Lab projects/stakeholders
8	27 public servants from Direction of Innovation of the Tourist Offer + Direction of Technological Innovation Centers for Crafts and Tourism	Ideas: -Development of workshops with participation of at least one coworker from all the Directions of the Vice Ministry of Tourism. -Visit new spaces in order to feel the real needs of population -Visit laboratories that are applying design methodologies -Continue the dynamics with public servants in order to generate more, new and better solutions and public services.
9	31 participants (FabLabs + public servants from MINCETUR)	Results: -Participation of FabLabs, makerspaces or labs from Pontificia Universidad Catolica del Peru, UTEC, ESAN, Universidad San Martin de Porres, UPC, Universidad Nacional de Ingenieria and Toulouse Lautrec. -Learning about how to use MIRO as a collaborative platform to cocreate and work remotely. -Fast prototypes with 3D printers and exploration of Virtual Reality. -6 proposals about how the MINCETUR Lab web page should be and what it should communicate to MINCETUR's social networks followers.
10	70 artisans and entrepreneurs	Results: -Collaborative work between artisans and entrepreneurs who hadn't know each other -Exploration of design thinking methodology to propose new handicrafts based on needs, local resources and FabLab technologies. -6 proposals of handicrafts based on 3D printing technology
11	20 American students coming for exchange (Emzingo)	Results*: -Learning about endangered species from Peru, according to the Red List Index. -4 ideas of tourism solutions/experiences based on a list of the endangered species using biomimicry.

# of intervention in chronological order	Participants (type of intervention)	Findings
		*This activity has been the last intervention and the first one to pilot the dynamic of proposing tourism solutions based on non-human actors (endangered animals in Peru from the Red List Index, indicator where peruvian economy is low: 103/117 global economies)

In the dynamics, the public servants of MINCETUR intervened mainly, and feedback was received from representatives of public entities such as the Secretariat of Government and Digital Transformation of the Presidency of the Council of Ministers, the National Council of Science, Technology and Technological Innovation - CONCYTEC and representatives of the Fab Lab network of Peru, in addition to the contributions of the Master in Design for Distributed Innovation -MDDI's professors. This allowed obtaining different points of view on the needs and the form of the project, in such a way that it can be sustainable over time.

Figure 1: Intervention 1 with public servants from Information Technology Office

Although there was participation and interest, through interviews with public servants and as part of the findings in the process, it was identified that (1) at the beginning there was no clear understanding of digital design and manufacturing applied to the tourism sector, which was collected from the meetups and demonstrations of digital manufacturing in the ministry, (2) public servants have never had spaces and moments to devise and prototype new solutions to local and global challenges in the tourism sector, considering that the building does not have the infrastructure to generate participatory dynamics and that remote work is being further reduced, therefore an absence of spaces is observed, (3) the perception is maintained that the only actors involved in the tourism sector are human beings without considering other living species, animals or plants which is obtained from conversations with legal advisors who govern their decisions and opinions based on the Political Constitution of Peru of 1993, (4) when referring to the connection with the academic sector, it is only considered those universities and institutes where they teach careers related to tourism but not careers related to the creative industries or STEAM, such as design, engineering, biology, education, data sciences, among others, which is also understood from conversations with public servants and the General Tourism National Law, which states that collaboration would happen only with those institutions where they teach tourism, (5) there is a lack of projects where the academic sector is linked with the public sector evidenced from the Global Innovation Index 2022 and the absence of formal agreements with educational institutions, (6) an isolated work is maintained due to the distribution of work spaces and the absence of rooms for creative, collaborative and communicative

work, and (7) the sustainability of a project is more possible to be achieved if more stakeholders are involved during the process and feel part of it.

Likewise, based on the Fab City Full Stack methodology and its 7 levels, it has been possible to identify the corresponding action and the actors involved (Table 2).

Table 2: Fab City Full Stack for MINCETUR Lab

Level of Full Stack	Activity	Stakeholders to be involved
Sharing knowledge with global network	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Hosts of remote event “Pacific Alliance: Tourism 4.0” with participation of Colombia, Chile, México, Argentina and Spain. -Asia-Pacific Economic Cooperation (APEC) project proposal “Impact of Creative Economies on the Future of Tourism in the APEC region” with co-sponsorship of 8 economies: Australia, Chile, China, Indonesia, Singapore, Russia, USA and Viet Nam -Paper for Fab23 Bhutan “From Public Servants to Co-creators: Design of MINCETUR Lab with the Fab City Full Stack methodology to innovate the tourism sector” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Public servants (from Peru and other countries) -Direction of Facilitation and Tourist Culture (in MINCETUR) -APEC (The Asia-Pacific Economic Cooperation) including 21 countries -Pacific Alliance -CAN (Comunidad Andina) -OECD (The Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development) -WTTC (World Travel & Tourism Council) -UNWTO (World Tourism Organization is the United Nations) -ATTA (Adventure Travel Trade Association) -WEF (World Economic Forum) -Fab Lab network -Nature
Applying bioregional strategies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Design of products (crafts) and services from biomaterials, biomimicry and speculation between cities (pilot) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -public servants -artesans -tour guides -entrepreneurs -students from public and private universities/institutes -citizens living in Peru -CITE (Centros de Innovación Productiva y Transferencia Tecnológica) -nature /animals -Fab Lab network
Prototyping place-based interventions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Exploration of digital fabrication technologies to turn ideas into products 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -public servants -artesans -tour guides -tourists -vacationists -entrepreneurs

Level of Full Stack	Activity	Stakeholders to be involved
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -students from public and private universities/institutes -citizens living in Peru -public servants -social networks followers -animals -nature -majors
Orchestrating efforts between local communities and initiatives	-Exchange of information between public servants, FabLabs and academia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -public servants -artesans -tour guides -tourists -vacationists -entrepreneurs -students from public & private universities/institutes -citizens living in Peru -social networks followers -animals -nature
Incubating value-generating projects	-Internal challenge to propose solutions based on data (in process of design)	-public servants and main director from organigram.
Enabling new forms of learning	-Sharing links about new concepts and tinkering workshops	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -SERVIR (Autoridad Nacional del Servicio Civil) offers mandatory and optional training -GIZ (German Cooperation) -Human Resource Office -public servants
Developing infrastructure and technologies for local production	-Identification of stakeholders and turning into horizontal talk between public servants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -public servants -CAS (administrative contract of services) -By trust (directors, vice ministers) OS (service providers temporal contract) Key actors: -support from legal advisor for everything -communicators

6 Results

The application of Fab City Full Stack learned during the Master in Design for Distributed Innovation (MDDI), the lessons learned from experiences in Fab Lab network and the constant feedback from the interactions with public servants from MINCETUR and stakeholders from the public, private, educational sectors, and citizens, together with the programmed activities of the ministry itself, have allowed the diffusion of the project and the creation of new activities for the upcoming months:

1. As part of the experience with public servants and stakeholders, there was already a first socialisation of the MINCETUR Lab project during the Virtual International Forum event: "Tourism 4.0: Towards the transformation of a smart tourist destination", within the framework of the

Pacific Alliance (Figure 2), which had the participation of 340 participants from Colombia, Chile, Mexico, Argentina and Spain, including SEGITTUR (State Society for the Management of Innovation and Tourism Technologies).

Figure 2: Presentation of MINCETUR Lab to the Pacific Alliance

2. From the co-creation session of the MINCETUR Lab’s website (intervention #9) (Figure 3), which had the participation of public servants of MINCETUR and representatives of FabLabs and makerspaces in educational institutions such as PUCP, UNI, ESAN, UTEC, USMP, UPC and Toulouse Lautrec, it is being developed a first prototype of a platform (following the Peruvian State guidelines) that will allow citizens and users of the ministry to share the lessons learned from the creative process, allowing a better connection and interaction with tourism service providers, artisans, public servants, and profiles linked to academia such as researchers, teachers, and students. Currently, the proposal is already approved and in the development process thanks to the support and participation of the MINCETUR Information Technology Office.

Figure 3: Intervention #9 between public servants and FabLabs and labs in Peru

3. As part of the Creative Economy axis of MINCETUR Lab, the project proposal called “Impact of Creative Economies on the Future of Tourism in the APEC region” has been developed and is in the process of review, in addition to having the co-sponsorship of 8 economies: Australia, Chile, China, Indonesia, Singapore, Russia, USA and Viet Nam. The project design contemplates as results a research paper with 8 study cases, a manual/guideline of the application of the creative economy in the public management focused on tourism, as well as two knowledge exchange sessions (remote and face-to-face) for the year 2024. The event is designed to have a goal of 8 economies as case studies, 40% participation of women, 80 participants during the in-person event and 70% awareness about the significance of creative economies in tourism, all using quantitative and qualitative measurement tools.
4. Despite political conflicts happening in the country, there has been an increase in collaborative projects between the directions of MINCETUR, and more commitment to share lessons learned

between co-workers, learn from stakeholders and work together with the academic sector to explore the use of new technologies to solve needs from the tourism and crafts sector.

7 Conclusions

- There is a strong need for spaces and moments in MINCETUR in order to share feelings, ideas, needs and complaints from the public servants.
- There is a lack of collaborative projects between the public and academic sector, which is one of the indicators from the Global Innovation Index, representing a great opportunity to discover new ideas from students and researchers based on real needs of the tourism and crafts sector.
- Technology is still a pain for many public servants from tourism and craft public sector, because they have never had the opportunity to learn or use them, and some reasons are the lack of time, the excess of work they have, the lack of a physical space to explore them, the weak connection with the Peruvian and global innovation ecosystem, and not being part of the educational curricula in careers linked to tourism.
- The development of interventions with different stakeholders helps understand a variety of perspectives about the same problem, meaning that the participation of people from different ages, studies, origin and mindset can help the creation of more inclusive solutions.
- There is a need to study the public sector since the mindset of public servants might be different from the makers, academics, entrepreneurs and private service providers, since they have to look for new ways to improve public services for human and non-human actors, but don't tend to research, develop, innovate or profit from services.
- Fab City Full Stack helps identify the existence of systems, what they are, how they work and why they exist in 7 levels, based on stakeholders distributed in different parts of the world.
- Non-human stakeholders and words such as "planet", "nature", "animals" are being included in the project (intervention #11) because they also have a role in tourism; however, there should be more pilots of planet centred design services because the concept is not well understood or unknown by public servants from Peru.
- The developed interactions have lasted between 1 hour to 3 hours because a group of public servants feel they need to "finish their tasks"; therefore, it is important to find the best time to make them happen and how long it might take for them to participate, which might differ in different contexts.
- A strategy of commitment still needs to be designed, explored and tested since it is uncertain the reaction of public servants if activities last more than one day.

8 Relevance

The paper shows the process that implies the formal creation of a laboratory from the perception of the public sector and the necessary strategies for its implementation and sustainability over time. In this way, this experience can be replicated or analysed by representatives of the tourism sector, policy makers, directors, ministers, managers, researchers and students in other countries with the aim of implementing public innovation spaces or laboratories linked to the tourism sector, with a focus on citizen and users participation and connection to the FabLab network.

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